

First records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Coreidae) and *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) in Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT: The first records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Coreidae) and *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) for Uzbekistan are reported. Additional information on the distribution of both species, mainly in Europe, is summarised.

KEY WORDS: *Leptoglossus occidentalis*, *Zelus renardii*, invasive species, first records, distribution, Uzbekistan.

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The western conifer seed bug *Leptoglossus* invasive in other regions of the world.

occidentalis Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) and the leafhopper assassin bug *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae), both species with a Nearctic origin, are

In Europe, *L. occidentalis* has colonised nearly all parts of the continent (van der Heyden, 2019), while *Z. renardii* can mainly be found in the Mediterranean Region (Kment & van der Heyden, 2022).

Now, both species can be reported for Uzbekistan in Central Asia:

On 24.10.2022, a single specimen of *Z. renardii* was found in Tashkent, the capital of Uzbekistan (Fig. 1). Photos of the specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist by Bulat Khaydarov (Khaydarov, 2022a). The specimen was found on a kitchen table in a private household. The botanical garden of Tashkent had been visited two days before. Thus, the specimen might have been brought from there (Bulat Khaydarov, pers. comm.). It is also possible that the specimen had been introduced to Tashkent with imported fruits, e.g. grapes from the Mediterranean Region, as it had happened in other cases (van der Heyden, 2021), but no such fruits were bought by the family of Bulat Khaydarov (pers. comm.).

On 25.11.2022, a single specimen of *L. occidentalis* was found in Tashkent. Photos of the specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist by Bulat Khaydarov (Khaydarov, 2022b). Five years ago, *L. occidentalis* was reported from Kazakhstan (Barclay & Nikolaeva, 2018).

It seems possible that *L. occidentalis* arrived in Uzbekistan from its neighbouring country in the north.

As *L. occidentalis* and *Z. renardii* have not been reported for Uzbekistan in scientific publications yet, the records reported in this note are the first ones of both species for this country.

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 24.10.2022. (Photo: Bulat Khaydarov).